

SELECTIVE REMOVAL OF IRON FROM FERRUGINOUS BAUXITE

By M. H. KHUNDKAR AND NAIMUDDIN AHMAD

APPLIED CHEMISTRY LABORATORY, DACCA UNIVERSITY, EAST PAKISTAN

(Received February 16, 1954)

Treatment of ferruginous bauxite with HCl gas converts a maximum of nearly 60% of iron at 750° into chloride. Simultaneous flow of hydrogen and hydrochloric acid vapour makes no improvement. But if the ore is first reduced with hydrogen (to FeO) prior to treatment with HCl gas, preferential removal of iron is most satisfactory.

At 750°, in 4 hours, over 98.2% of the iron can thus be eliminated, leaving a residue almost white and having an iron oxide content of less than 0.15%. For this, of course, a high space velocity of 7.25 c.c./min./g. of ore is required. With a space velocity of nearly 3.00 c.c./min./g. of ore, the extent of elimination would decrease by about 10%. The alumina remains absolutely unaffected even up to 900°. The titania may be eliminated separately by using a temperature higher than 750° (which is optimum for removal of iron).

Presence of iron oxide renders ferruginous bauxite ores unsuitable for the manufacture of aluminium salts (for dyeing and paper sizing in particular) and for refractories. As a result, selective removal of iron from such ores has been the subject of many investigations, a comprehensive review of which has been made by Fink and Marchi¹.

Treatment at a high temperature with a mixture of chlorine and carbon monoxide², chlorination in presence of carbon³ or treatment with sulphur chlorides⁴ have long been the subjects of different patents but these do not seem to have been exploited on a commercial scale. Recently, Fink and Marchi¹ claimed a remarkable improvement in the process of elimination of iron by a prior sulphiding of the ore. Even in this process a maximum elimination of only 90% has been achieved.

Treatment of bauxite ores with HCl gas has been less thoroughly studied. Buiman and Rennerfelt⁵ treated bauxite ores with a reducing agent such as carbon, carbon monoxide or hydrogen at a sufficiently high temperature to render the alumina insoluble, but below the melting point of the material, and then removing the reduced iron with HCl solution or chlorine gas. A repetition of the steps was claimed to have ensured complete elimination of iron.

Patrouilleau⁶ leached out iron oxide with HCl in an organic solvent such as ether or acetone. Voisin⁷ reported the elimination of iron by heating in a stream of HCl gas at 150°-500°, with or without a small amount of chlorine,

but without any reducing agent. This appears rather strange, as at the temperature range mentioned, ferric oxide must take an unusually long time to react. On the other hand, the high temperature used by Rennerfelt⁵ may be unnecessary, as thermodynamic considerations show that FeO itself is reactive towards HCl gas. The present investigation was thus undertaken on a comprehensive study of the treatment of bauxite with HCl vapour under different conditions.

EXPERIMENTAL

The bauxite used in this investigation contained a relatively high proportion of silica and iron oxide: $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 = 60.40\%$; $\text{SiO}_2 = 18.55\%$; $\text{Fe}_2\text{O}_3 = 8.50\%$; $\text{TiO}_2 = 2.05\%$; loss on ignition = 10.50% (by difference). Other inorganic impurities were absent.

For most experiments, these were powdered to 100 mesh (except one series where the effect of particle size was studied), dried at 105° in an air-oven and then kept as stock samples.

For a particular experiment, a weighed quantity of the stock sample was taken in a porcelain boat and kept within a silica reaction tube inside a laboratory tube furnace in such a position that when the furnace was heated up to a particular temperature, the ore remained at a uniform temperature zone. The furnace was electrically heated. The temperature was controlled with the help of a rheostat and measured by Pt/Pt-Rh thermocouple in conjunction with a Cambridge Temperature Indicator.

After placing the ore in the proper position, the reaction tube was connected to the gas inlet system and the temperature raised to the desired range. As the steady temperature was attained, the desired gas (purified according to the usual methods) was passed for a given time. After cooling the products of reaction, the water-soluble fraction (HCl-soluble fraction in some cases) was analysed for iron, aluminium and titanium. The residue was collected, dried and heated to drive off any moisture and then the iron content of it was determined.

In a few preliminary experiments before high temperature studies with HCl gas, attempts were made to dissolve out the iron oxide with HCl. The oven-dried sample (2.0 g.) was boiled with dilute HCl solution (100 c.c., 1 + 4 v/v); 27.1% of Fe_2O_3 dissolved, but at the same time 6.3% of Al_2O_3 present was also dissolved. Treatment of the ore first with hydrogen gas at 750° for 3 hours and then repeating the process showed a dissolution of only 17.6% of iron oxide and 6.7% of alumina. Subsequent treatment of either product

with more concentrated acid solutions could dissolve out considerably greater percentage of the iron oxide, but the simultaneous dissolution of alumina also increased. On the whole, neither of the processes is suitable for preferential elimination of iron.

Results of treatment with HCl gas at elevated temperature (Table I) show some improvement over the room temperature treatment with HCl solutions, in that alumina remains unaffected.

TABLE I

Treatment of ferruginous bauxite with HCl gas at diff. temp.
Bauxite taken = 2.0 g. (100 mesh). HCl gas at 14-15 c.c./min. for
3 hours at max. temp.

Temp.	Removal of diff. constituents in water extract.			Fe ₂ O ₃ content of the residue.	Colour of residue.
	Fe ₂ O ₃ .	Al ₂ O ₃ .	TiO ₂ .		
400°	23.5%	1.7%	Nil	6.75%	Brick-red
600°	47.1	0.67	"	4.80	"
700°	55.8	Trace	"	3.90	Light red
750°	58.8	Nil	"	3.85	"
*750°	61.2	"	"	3.75	"
800°	48.2	"	"	4.70	Red
850°	47.5	"	"	4.85	"

*HCl vapour passed for 4 hours.

The products of all the above reactions were extracted with water. Elimination of iron was not remarkably high (58.8% in 3 hours, 61.2% in 4 hours at 750°) under conditions of the experiments. The residues were in all cases somewhat reddish as expected.

Similar experiments as above were carried out at different temperatures (Table II) in a stream of both hydrogen and HCl gas. Quite contrary to expectation, yields were unsatisfactory, and in fact, no improvement was obtained over that due to HCl gas alone. The space velocities of both gases were rather high. The residue were in all cases black, showing the presence of FeO. It thus appears that some of the FeO formed had no opportunity of reacting with HCl vapour.

In a third series of experiments, the ore was treated at different temperatures first with hydrogen gas for a definite time (3 hours) and then HCl gas was passed at the same temperature for desired length of time. Results are shown in Table II. Curves in Fig. 1 represent the elimination of iron from the ore under different conditions of treatment (in 3 hours). All curves show a maximum corresponding to 750°. These experiments were all carried out for

definite periods of time and not up to the equilibrium stage, so that the progress of reaction at any particular solid temperature would depend on the rate of reaction and the reactivity of the solid phase involved. Decreasing conversions above

FIG. 1

also fairly rapid at 700°. The optimum temperature should thus be above 700° and as near to 750° as possible.

Action of the above gases on alumina was negligible. The aluminium content of the water extract was in all cases looked for, but found too low to warrant any quantitative report (always less than 0.2%). The elimination of titanium is more interesting. Up to 750° (optimum for elimination of iron), a maximum of only 10% of total titania content is acted on; whereas, more than 50% of the titania is removed at 900°.

Effect of particle size and space velocity.—The ore was obtained in the form of small pea size globules (6-8 mm. in diameter), somewhat brownish red and of a visibly uniform composition inside the globules. Previous experiments were all carried out with ore of particle size of about 100 mesh. The optimum temperature having been found out, the efficiency of the reaction was then studied

750°, would be due to decreased reactivity of the solid oxide, due to its crystallisation. Distinctly higher conversion of FeO to the corresponding chloride (i.e. in experiments with hydrogen followed by HCl gas) confirms the thermodynamic observations. The conversion of FeO at 750° in 3 hours is in itself quite promising, being over 97.5%. The residual alumina contained less than 0.1-0.2% of ferric oxide. The product was an absolutely white mass. Under the same conditions, in four hours the elimination was 98.2%, the residual alumina containing only traces of iron oxide. The reaction was

with reference to the particle size of the solid reactant. In the gas-solid reaction, this factor must play an important role as indeed would be found from results in Table III.

TABLE III

Effect of particle size of ferruginous bauxite on its treatment with HCl gas.

Temp. = 750° H₂ passed for 3 hours. at 8-9 c.c./min., followed by HCl gas at 14-15 c.c./min.

Ore taken.	Particle size.	Fe ₂ O ₃ removed.
5.0 g.	Lumps (6-8 mm. diam.)	25.3%
5.0	10-20 mesh	40.1
5.0	20-40	60.5
5.0	90-100	87.0
2.0	90-100	97.7

With the original particles, results were unsatisfactory, but still nearly a fourth of the total iron content was eliminated. Other conditions remaining the same, the extent of iron removal (by HCl vapour) increases with decreasing particle size. A comparison of the last two experiments indicates that the extent of reaction is also dependent on the space velocity. A more complete picture can be had from Table IV.

TABLE IV

Effect of space velocity on the treatment of ferruginous bauxite with HCl gas under optimum conditions.

Temp. = 750°. H₂ passed for 3 hours, at 8-9 c.c./min., followed by HCl vapour at 14-15 c.c./min.

Ore taken.	Space velocity of HCl vapour (c.c./min./g. of ore).	Fe ₂ O ₃ removed.
2.0g.	7.25	97.7%
5.0	2.90	87.0
10.0	1.45	50.5

It would be noted that instead of changing the rate of flow of HCl vapour in the different experiments, the amount of bauxite input was changed in order to observe the effects of space velocity. As is expected, the reaction is favoured by a high space velocity of HCl vapour. For favourable reaction, minimum space velocity of 3.0 c.c./min./g. of ore seems essential. Otherwise complete elimination of iron even under optimum conditions may take an unusually long time, or may not be possible at all. With space velocity between 3.0 and 8.0 c.c./min./g. the reaction would possibly go to completion, the time being less, the greater the space velocity.

R E F E R E N C E S

1. Fink & Marchi, *Trans. Electrochem. Soc.*, 1938, 74, 469.
2. Bergius & Co., Ger. Pat., 40, 393/1887.
3. Dearborn, Canadian P., 283, 609/1928.
4. Jenness, U. S. P., 1, 858, 272/1932.
5. Buiman & Rennerfelt, B. P., 369, 244/1932.
6. Patrouilleau, F. P., 481, 106/1916. Cf. Farbenindustrie, I. G., Ger. Patent, 573, 283/1930.
7. Voisin, B. P., 306, 094/1929.
8. Kellogg, *J. Met.-Trans.*, AIME, 1951, 188, 862.
9. Croft, *J. Appl. Chem.*, 1952, 2, 562.
10. Evans & Kubaschewski, "Metallurgical Thermochemistry", Butterworth (London), 1951.